

Species Richness of Avifauna in Four Long Term Ecological Research Sites in Mindanao, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The Philippines has diverse avifauna especially on the island of Mindanao which has the highest percentage of forest cover. This study was conducted to assess the species richness and distribution of avian species in four Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) sites in Mindanao, namely: Mts. Apo, Kitanglad, Hamiguitan, and Malindang. Mist netting for a total of 857 net days and point surveys (62 hours) were carried out inside and along the 1-ha permanent plot to document bird species in the area. Sixty-five bird species belonging to 30 families and 49 genera were recorded. Of the four forest ecosystems, Mt. Apo showed the highest species richness (38 species), endemism (58.33%), and species diversity while Mt. Hamiguitan showed the least species richness (20 species). *Pachycephalophilippinensis* was the only species recorded in all LTER sites. Percentage similarity of the species composition across LTER sites was below 55% indicating that each of the four LTER sites showcased a unique avian composition.

KEY WORDS: Birds, Mt. Apo, Mt. Hamiguitan, Mt. Kitanglad, Mt. Malindang.

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine archipelago which is composed of 7,100 distinct islands [1] is considered as one of the mega diverse countries due to its unique composition of flora and fauna, where high species richness and endemism are observed. The country's geologic history and long period of isolation from the rest of the world have produced varied land forms, water bodies, and climatic conditions and these, in turn, have contributed to its high species diversity and endemism [2]. However, the great biodiversity and endemism in the country [3] are mostly threatened due to continued deforestation and habitat destruction [4] which could lead to the decline of wildlife population [5] and shall likely lead to its extinction [3]. For birds alone, the Philippines has a total of 576 species, and after more than a decade, the discovery of new species increases [6]. Lepage [7] reported that the Philippines is now home to 676 bird species in which 222 are endemic and 90 are globally threatened. Of the bird species recorded in the country, 325 are geographically restricted to Mindanao with 96 endemic [6]. Mindanao which is one of the major islands in the Philippines still has rich biological resources and has the largest remaining forest cover [8]. The study of Nuñez *et al.* [9] reported a total of 161 species of birds in Mt. Malindang and 272 species were recorded in Mt. Apo [10]. According to Relox *et al.* [11], Mt. Hamiguitan harbors 53 bird species and Peterson *et al.* [12] reported 198 species in Mt. Kitanglad. But these diverse places are subject to the continuous habitat destruction which could lead to habitat loss, considered as one of the major problems at present. In spite of habitat degradation, there are many new species that are still being discovered [13]. Two new species of Hawk Owl, namely, Camiguin Hawk-Owl *Ninox leventisi* sp. n. and the Cebu Hawk Owl *Ninox rumseyi* sp. n. were discovered by Rasmussen *et al.* [14].

The ecological services that birds provide are crucial and irreplaceable [15]. Birds are also valuable indicators of global patterns in biodiversity conservation [16] and field study on birds is an information key for assessing extinction risks across the avifauna as a whole and, at a local level, to provide clear conservation prescriptions to management authorities [17]. Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) helps address these complex environmental challenges by providing comprehensive information to the broader ecological community, general public, resource managers and policy makers and aims to conserve, protect, and manage ecosystems at local, regional and global scales, their biodiversity, and the service they provide [18]. However, long term studies on various aspects of biodiversity in the Philippines are few [19] and monitoring studies on fauna in Mindanao forests through establishment of long-term ecological research (LTER) sites are lacking. Thus, this paper presents the recent updates on the species composition, diversity, and endemism of birds in the one-hectare plot of each of the four LTER sites in Mindanao.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling sites

This study was conducted in the 1-ha permanent plots in the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) sites established in Mt. Malindang, Mt. Apo, Mt. Kitanglad, and Mt. Hamiguitan in Mindanao (Figure.1).

Figure 1. Study sites in Mindanao [20] are presented in triangles: Mt. Apo (▲); Mt. Kitanglad (▲); Mt. Hamiguitan (▲); Mt. Malindang (▲).

Site 1 is in the upper montane forest of Mt. Apo at an altitude of 1,900-2000 meters above sea level (masl) with coordinates 6°59'47''N, 125°15'12''E. Temperature range during sampling was 13-19°C. The site has a close-canopy layer and inhabited by trees and shrubs (*Ascarinaphilippinensis*, *Clethracanescens*, *Ardisi* sp.), herbs and epiphytes (*Freycineti* sp., *Sarcopyramisnepalensis*, *Hedyotis* sp. and *Sarcandra* sp.), and fern allies (*Plagiogyriachristi*, *Alsophilaheterochlamydea*, *Tmesipteris zamora*, *Lindsaealinear*is). Soil litter was thick (≈20 to 25 mm) and moist. Fallen trees and other plants were observed to be present. The distance of the area to the nearest water body (stream) is around 100-300 m. In this site, three sampling visits with a total of 15 sampling days were carried out on November 15-18, 2012, February 5-10, 2013, and May 4-9, 2013.

Site 2 is a lower montane forest in Mt. Hamiguitan at an altitude of 1000-1100 masl with coordinates 6°43'58''N, 126°9'58''E. Temperature range during sampling was 18-25°C. The area has a close to slightly open canopy layer and inhabited by various types of trees and shrubs (*Syzygium* sp., *Palaquium* sp., *Terminalia* sp., *Calophyllum blancoi* and *Syzygium simile*), herbs and epiphytes (*Freycineti* sp., *Appendicula* sp., *Calamus* sp., *Cfmerrillii*, *Piper aduncum* and *Agalmyla* sp.), and ferns and fern allies (*Selaginellainvolvens*, *Tapeinidium pinnatum*, *Oreogrammitis fasciata*, *Lindsaealongifolia*, *Selliguea triloba* and *Lindsaeahamiguitanensis*). Moist soil litter was moderately present (≈10 to 15 mm). Fallen trees and other plants were moderate in abundance. Running water was observed in some areas inside the plot while stagnant rain water was observed in the creek along the boundary of the plot. In this site, two sampling visits with a total of 12 sampling days were carried out on January 25-30, 2013 and April 3-8, 2013.

Site 3 is at the upper montane forest of Mt. Kitanglad at 2100-2200 masl with coordinates 8°5'46''N, 124°55'17''E. Temperature ranged from 9-17°C during the sampling. The close-canopy layer (some areas are slightly open) is inhabited by trees and shrubs (*Flacourtiarukam*, *Prunus* sp., *Alsophilafuliginosa*, *Mastixiatrichotoma* and *Phyllocladushypophyllus*), herbs and epiphytes (*Sarcandra* sp., *Sarcopyramisnepalensis*, *Agalmyla* sp., *Elatostemapulcherrima* and *Piper aduncum*), and ferns and fern allies (*Asplenium normale*, *Lycopodium clavatum*, *Huperzia serrata*, *Acrophorus nodosus*, *Hymenophyllum* sp., *Prosapti* sp., and *Plagiogyriaglauca*). Soil litter is thick to average (≈22 to 40 mm) in abundance while moist, fallen trees and other plants were moderately present. The distance of the plot to the nearest body of water

(stream) was around 150-350 m. In this site, four sampling visits with a total of 14 sampling days were carried out on December 16-18, 2012, May 27-30, 2013, October 27-30, 2013, and December 16-18, 2013.

Site 4 is located at the upper montane forest of Mt. Malindang at 1600-1700 masl with coordinates 8°17'45" N, 123°36'34" E. Temperature during the sampling ranged from 14-25°C. The close to slightly open canopy layer was inhabited by various types of trees, palm and shrubs (*Hydrangea scandens*, *Macaranga dipterocarpifolia*, *Eusideroxylon zwageri*, *Ficus odorata*, *Justicia* sp. and *Pinangaphilippinensis*), herbs and epiphytes (*Impatiens platypetala*, *Freycinetia* sp., *Piper aduncum*, *Gomphostemma javanicum* and *Elatostema pulcherrimum*), and ferns and fern allies (*Selaginella involvens*, *Huperzia squarrosa*, *Asplenium decorum*, *Asplenium phyllitidis*, and *Araiosstegia hymenophylloides*). Soil litter is moderate to average (≈10 to 15 mm). Fallen trees and other plants were found to be moderate in number. Although stagnant rain water was observed near the plot, the distance of the plot to the nearest body of water (stream) is around 1000+ m. The distance of the plot to the nearest anthropogenic area is around 700-1000 m. In this site, three sampling visits with a total of 17 sampling days were carried out on February 22-28, 2013 and December 7-11, 2013.

Sampling, Processing, and Identification

Birds were captured using mist nets with four shelves; each net was 12 m in length and 4 m in width. Twelve mist nets were installed inside the 20m x 20m subplot inside the one-hectare permanent plot and three were installed at the borders of the permanent plots. Mist nets were monitored from 0500-1700 hours at 1-2 hours interval and checked again in the early morning. Further, an ocular survey/point counting was performed along the boundaries and inside the 1-hectare plot in each site. Twelve-point stations with a distance ranging from 20-30 meters were established. In every point station all bird species that were observed were counted. The entire sampling had a total of 857 net-days where 210 net days were accomplished in Mt. Apo, 242 net-days in Mt. Kitanglad, 155 net-days in Mt. Hamiguitan, and 250 net-days in Mt. Malindang. Standard external measurements (total length, tail length, wing, tarsus, bill, eye color, ventral and dorsal color) were taken. Identified species of birds were tagged, measured and released at the site of capture. Guide to Philippine birds by Kennedy *et al.* [6] was used for the identification. Two to three individuals per species were kept as voucher specimens. Species diversity, species abundance and similarity of species composition were determined using BIOPRO software version 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sixty-five avian species in 30 families and 49 genera were documented (Table 1). Mt. Apo was the most species-rich (38 species), while the least number of species was recorded in Mt. Hamiguitan (20 species). Avian species richness increases as elevation increases and peaked at the upper-montane forest of Mt. Apo at 1944 masl and gradually decreases as the elevation goes higher in Mt. Kitanglad's transitional zone between montane and mossy forest at 2200 masl. This result is in agreement with Peterson *et al.* [12] that species richness is low at the lowest elevation, high in the foothill forests and middle elevation and eventually declines in the high elevation. Shiu and Lee [21] reported that bird species richness tends to decline on high elevation whereas species richness remains roughly constant in low elevation. Moreover, as elevation increases, the availability of resources for birds diminishes reflecting differences in forest stand structure, vegetation composition, site productivity, secondary biotic interactions, distribution pattern and available land area [22, 23, 24, 25] which partly explains the high species richness of birds at the upper-montane forest of Mt. Apo having an elevation of 1900 masl. Besides, Mt. Apo has approximately 40-55 tree species in a one-hectare plot with a wide diversity in plant community types [10]. According to Joshi *et al.* [26], avian species richness is positively correlated with the plant species diversity and foliage height diversity. Montane vegetation is believed to be the ecotone between lowland and mossy forest which shows high diversity of plants and offers various food options for birds which are further explained through edge effects. Edge effects refer to the influence of the proximity and number of nearby forest edges, edge age, weather events, structure and composition of the adjoining matrix vegetation on the number of animal species present in the direct vicinity [27, 28]. On the other hand, the reason for Mt. Hamiguitan's low species richness is related to its condition having an ultramafic soil [29] that is characterized by a high concentration of heavy metal content [30] which is a major reason for the sparse vegetation [31] and stressful environment for plant growth that leads to poor plant productivity in the mountain ecosystem [32, 33].

Table 1. Species Richness, Conservation status, and Distribution status of Birds in Four LTER sites.

Taxa	Common Name	Conservation Status	Distribution Status	Mt. Apo (1944 masl)	Mt. Kitanglad (2200 masl)	Mt. Hamiguitan (1100 masl)	Mt. Malindang (1620 masl)
ACCIPITRIDAE							
1	<i>Accipiter virgatus</i>	Besra	LC	NE	1		
ALCEDINIDAE							
2	<i>Actenoideshombroni</i>	Blue-capped Kingfisher	Vu	ME			3
APODIDAE							
3	<i>Collocaliaesculenta</i>	Glossy Swiftlet	LC	NE	4		1
CAMPEPHAGIDAE							
4	<i>Coracinastrata</i>	Bar-bellied Cuckooshrike	LC	NE	4		
COLUMBIDAE							
5	<i>Chalcophapsindica</i>	Common Emerald Dove	LC	NE	1		
6	<i>Duculaaenea</i>	Green Imperial-pigeon	LC	NE	7		
7	<i>Macropygiaphasianella</i>	Reddish cuckoo-dove	LC	NE	4	2	18
8	<i>Phapitreronleucotis</i>	White-eared brown-dove	LC	PE			2
9	<i>Phapitreronamethystinus</i>	Amethyst brown-dove	LC	PE	11	6	17
10	<i>Ptilinopusoccipitalis</i>	Yellow breasted fruit-dove	LC	PE	5	4	1
11	<i>Columba vitiensis</i>	Metallic pigeon	LC	NE		2	
CUCULIDAE							
12	<i>Cacomantimerulinus</i>	Plaintive Cuckoo	LC	NE	3		
13	<i>Cacomantisvariolosus</i>	Brush cuckoo	LC	NE	14	4	17
14	<i>Centropusmelanops</i>	Black-faced Coucal	LC	PE	2		6
15	<i>Cuculusfugax</i>	Hodgson's Hawk-cuckoo	LC	NE	2		
DICAEIDAE							
16	<i>Dicaeumastrale</i>	Red-keeled flowerpecker	LC	PE	1		2
17	<i>Dicaeumhypoleucum</i>	Buzzing flowerpecker	LC	PE			3

EURYLAIMIDAE								
18	<i>Eurylaimussteerii</i>	Mindanao Broadbill	Vu	PE	2	10		
FALCONIDAE								
19	<i>Microhieraxerythrogenys</i>	Philippine Falconet	LC	PE			2	
FRINGILLIDAE								
20	<i>Pyrrhulaleucogenis</i>	White-cheeked Bullfinch	LC	PE	2			
LANIIDAE								
21	<i>Laniuscristatus</i>	Brown shrike	LC	NE				2
22	<i>Laniusvalidirostris</i>	Mountain shrike	NT	PE	2			
23	<i>Laniusschach</i>	Long-tailed shrike	LC	NE				5
MONARCHIDAE								
24	<i>Hypothymisazurea</i>	Black-naped monarch	LC	NE			1	
MOTACILLIDAE								
25	<i>Anthusgustavi</i>	Pechora Pipit	LC	NE		1		
MUSCICAPIDAE								
26	<i>Culicicapahelianthea</i>	Citrine Canary Flycatcher	LC	NE	2			
27	<i>Eumyiaspanayensis</i>	Turquoise Flycatcher	LC	NE	3	3		10
28	<i>Ficedulahyperythra</i>	Snowy- browed flycatcher	LC	NE	3	2		4
29	<i>Ficedulawestermanni</i>	Little Pied Flycatcher	LC	NE		19		18
30	<i>Muscicapagriseisticta</i>	Grey-streaked Flycatcher	LC	NE	1			
31	<i>Rhinomyiasgoodfellowi</i>	Slaty-backed Jungle flycatcher	NT	ME	6			
32	<i>Rhinomyiasruficauda</i>	Rufous-tailed Jungle flycatcher	LC	NE			4	
NECTARINIIDAE								
33	<i>Aethopygaboltoni</i>	Apo Sunbird	NT	ME	2			
34	<i>Aethopygalinaraborae</i>	Lina's Sunbird	NT	ME			6	
35	<i>Aethopygapulcherrima</i>	Metallic-winged Sunbird	LC	PE		2	10	2
36	<i>Aethopygashelleyi</i>	Lovely Sunbird	LC	PE		1		

37	<i>Aethopygaprigenia</i>	Grey-hooded Sunbird	NT	ME				7
38	<i>Nectariniajugularis</i>	Olive-backed Sunbird	LC	NE				3
PACHYCEPHALIDAE								
39	<i>Pachycephalaalbiventris</i>	Green-backed Whistler	LC	PE	3			
40	<i>Pachycephalaphilippinensis</i>	Yellow-bellied Whistler	LC	PE	12	19	9	21
PARIDAE								
41	<i>Paruselegans</i>	Elegant Tit	LC	PE		2	1	4
PICIDAE								
42	<i>Chrysocolapteslucidus</i>	Greater Flameback	LC	PE	3	6		1
PSITTACIDAE								
43	<i>Prioniturusdiscurus</i>	Blue-crowned Racquet-tail	LC	PE	15			
44	<i>Prioniturusmontanus</i>	Montane Racquet-tail	NT	PE		2		
PYCNONOTIDAE								
45	<i>Hypsipetesphilippinus</i>	Philippine bulbul	LC	PE	4	2	28	
46	<i>Pycnonotusgoiavier</i>	Yellow-vented bulbul	LC	NE				4
RALLIDAE								
47	<i>Amaurornisolivacea</i>	Plain bush-hen	LC	PE				1
RHIPIDURIDAE								
48	<i>Rhipiduranigrocinnamomea</i>	Black-and-cinnamon Fantail	LC	PE		6		31
49	<i>Rhipidurasuperciliaris</i>	Blue Fantail	LC	PE	2		5	1
SITTIDAE								
50	<i>Sittafrontalis</i>	Velvet-fronted Nuthatch	LC	NE		2	2	2
STRIGIDAE								
51	<i>Otusmegalotis</i>	Philippine Scops-owl	LC	PE		1	1	
STURNIDAE								
52	<i>Basilornismiranda</i>	Apo Myna	NT	ME	5			

53	<i>Sarcopsalvus</i>	Coletto	LC	PE	4			
SYLVIIDAE								
54	<i>Orthotomuscucullatus</i>	Mountain-tailor Bird	LC	NE			5	
55	<i>Phylloscopustrivirgatus</i>	Mountain Leaf Warbler	LC	NE	6	17		22
56	<i>Phylloscopusolivaceus</i>	Philippine Leaf-Warbler	LC	PE				1
TIMALIIDAE								
57	<i>Leonardinawoodi</i>	Bagobo Babbler	LC	PE	1			
58	<i>Macronousstriaticeps</i>	Brown-tit-babbler	LC	PE	1		1	10
TROGONIDAE								
59	<i>Harpactesardens</i>	Philippine Trogon	LC	PE			3	1
TURDIDAE								
60	<i>Brachypteryxmontana</i>	White-browed Shortwing	LC	NE	9	6		50
61	<i>Turdusobscurus</i>	Eyebrowed Thrush	LC	NE		1		1
62	<i>Turduspoliocephalus</i>	Island Thrush	LC	NE	3	11		12
ZOSTEROPIDAE								
63	<i>Hypocryptadiuscinnamomus</i>	Cinnamon Ibon	LC	ME	36	33		15
64	<i>Lophozosteropsgoodfellowi</i>	Black-masked White-eye	LC	PE	5	24		5
65	<i>Zosteropsmontanus</i>	Mountain White-eye	LC	NE	4	58	6	35
Total Individuals			865		195	246	125	299
Total Species			65		38	27	20	32
Total Endemic			36		21	14	14	16
Total Threatened			2		1	1	0	1
Total Mist net days/points survey hours			857/62		210/12	242/19	155/12	250/19

Legend: LC-Least Concern; Vu-Vulnerable; NE-Non-Endemic; PE-Philippine Endemic

According to Joshi *et al.* [26] vegetation structure of the habitat seems to be one of the key features which influences the avian species at local level and any reduction in extent or quality of this forest type will lead to a reduction in the population size of species. It appears that the low species richness in Mt. Hamiguitan is due to poor plant productivity and sparse vegetation in the area since birds are dependent on forest habitat with abundant vegetation for roosting and feeding. Cousin and Phillips [34] also reported that forest productivity and resource availability affect species richness. Rich soil, abundant moisture, and regular inputs of nutrients and biological materials result in a complex natural community [35] which is an important factor governing species richness and habitat selection of birds in an area [34]. The study of Mallari *et al.* [36] shows that avian species especially those understory key species are mostly found in areas containing large numbers of big trees, indicating that the presence of large trees is an important determinant of the suitability of habitat.

Among the birds, *Pachycephalophilippinensis* is the only species recorded in all LTER sites. Kennedy *et al.* [6] reported that this species is present in all elevational gradients. *Zosterops montanus* (11.91%, 103 individuals), *Hypocryptadius cinnamomeus* (9.71%), *Brachypteryx montana* (7.51%), and *Pachycephalophilippinensis* (7.05%) were the abundant birds noted.

Avian endemism across LTER sites was observed to be highest in Mt. Apo (58.33%), followed in decreasing order in Mts. Malindang (44.44%), Hamiguitan (38.89%) and Kitanglad (38.89%). High endemism in Mt. Apo is attributed to its habitat itself, where the composition of plant species varies from the rest of the LTER sites. According to UNESCO [10], the Pliocene-Quaternary volcanic terrain and high altitude of Mt. Apo provided opportunity for diversity of habitats. Paz *et al.* [37] found that elevation also had greatest influence on the endemic bird communities in an area.

The 65 avian species recorded in four LTER sites comprised about 10% of the total number of birds in the Philippines. The 32 species recorded in the 1-ha plot in Mt. Malindang forms 20% of the total number of birds reported by Nuñez *et al.* [9]. In Mt. Apo, 38 species were noted which comprised 13.97% of the total avian species recorded in the area [10]. The twenty species recorded in Mt. Hamiguitan comprised 37.74% of the total species reported by Ates *et al.* [38] who covered many sampling sites in Mt. Hamiguitan. Twelve bird species (*Aethopygalaraborae*, *Aethopygapulcherrima*, *Dicaeuma australe*, *Dicaeum hypoleucum*, *Hypothymis azurea*, *Microhierax erythrogenys*, *Orthotomuscucullatus*, *Otus megalotis*, *Paruselegans*, *Rhinomyias ruficauda*, *Rhipidurasuperciliaris*, and *Sitta frontalis*) were not documented in the montane vegetation in the study of Ates *et al.* [38] but 15 species (*Haliasturindus*, *Phapitreron leucotis*, *Chalcophaps indica*, *Dendrocopos maculatus*, *Pycnonotus goiavier*, *Pycnonotus roostictus*, *Rhipidurajavanica*, *Rhipiduranigrocinnamomea*, *Culicicapahelianthea*, *Aethopygaprimigenia*, *Cisticola axillis*, *Ptilocichlamindanensis*, *Sarcops calvus*, *Buceros hydrocorax*, *Penelopides panini*) earlier recorded were not documented in the present study at the same vegetation. The 27 species documented in Mt. Kitanglad comprised 16.16% of the total species recorded in the entire mountain ecosystem by Peterson *et al.* [12]. Results indicate that sampling in a larger area could increase the number of species than can be documented which coincides with the observation of Turner *et al.* [39] that the number of species encountered can be due to the number of areas (habitat types) sampled and the method used.

Among the four LTER sites, Mt. Apo is the most diverse place for avifauna (Figure 2). This just shows that Mt. Apo provides habitats and resources that support the needs of the avian fauna to survive. According to UNESCO [10] the topography and interactions of other factors such as, climate, soil, geology, slope, and drainage of Mt. Apo have allowed for the development of a wide diversity of plant community types and therefore could support a large diversity of fauna. Mt. Hamiguitan is not diverse enough in terms of avian species since this mountain has an ultramafic soil [40] which makes the habitat unproductive [41]. Soil with high content of heavy metals inhibits many plants to grow leading to less availability of food for birds. Heavy metals in the soil are arsenic, cadmium, chromium, cobalt, copper, iron, lead, manganese, mercury, nickel, zinc and lead [42, 43]. In addition, Chibuike and Obiora [44] stated that the high concentration of heavy metals in the soil leads to the reduction in plant growth, performance, and yield which eventually lead to food insecurity and low species richness of fauna. Furthermore, anthropogenic activities [44] such as habitat destruction by mining activity and other habitat stresses in Mt. Hamiguitan [45] increase the concentration of these elements to amounts that are harmful to both plants and animals [44]. The study of Kiikkilä [46] on the effect of heavy metals in the ecosystem showed that the low survival rate and breeding success of hole-nesting passerines were caused by habitat changes or the increase in the amounts of heavy metals and the quality of food in the area. On the other hand, bird assemblages or community are affected by factors like vegetation structure, food diversity and availability in the area [47, 48, 49]. Mt. Kitanglad is so far the coldest among the four LTER sites with temperature ranging from 10°C-18°C and has the highest elevation of 2200 masl. The low temperature at higher elevation may have limited the distribution of birds, which agrees with the findings of Peterson *et al.* [12] who found lower species richness of birds at higher elevations in Mt. Kitanglad Range. Further, Mt. Kitanglad was observed to have the largest amount of rainfall and strong wind since it was raining in every sampling period. Bird flights are intercepted during drastic weather conditions (e.g. downpours, torrents, strong winds) and thus bird species observation is usually low at that time. According to Stevens and O'Connor [50] abiotic factors such

as latitude, altitude, temperature, and rainfall could account for ultimate differences in the number of species in an area. A study conducted by Assunção–Albuquerque *et al.* [51] reported that climate is indeed one of the major factors that affect the species richness in the area. Furthermore, Cuetoandde Casenave [52] stated that among the numerous ecological factors that determine the spatial variation of bird species richness, climate seems to be important at the macrogeographic scale. In addition, habitat structure (usually measured through estimates of vegetation structure) is also related to variations in bird species richness and diversity.

Figure 2. Diversity values of birds in four LTER sites

Figure 3 shows that most of the avian species in the four LTER sites are discordant. The species are most likely unique in their location due to low similarity of species composition (< 57.00%). Mts. Kitanglad and Malindang are the most related sites since they have the highest similarity percentage (56.00%). This similarity is attributed to the season since most of the data collected were taken at almost the same month which covered the last week of November in Mt. Kitanglad and 1st week of December in Mt. Malindang both in the same year. Shiu and Lee [21] reported that differences in the season influence the evaluation of the distribution patterns of bird species richness and composition. Moreover, Mt. Apo is closely related to Mt. Kitanglad (40.87%) and this similarity is attributed to high elevation which is a common factor in the two mountains. Sampling sites in Mts. Apo (1900 masl) and Kitanglad (2200) are both located at the upper montane forest extending to the transition zone between montane and mossy forests, portraying high similarity of plant species composition thus offering almost the same resources for bird species. In addition, the ranges of temperature between these two mountains are almost the same. Among the four LTER sites, Mt. Hamiguitan is considered to be the most unique habitat in terms of bird composition. The uniqueness of Mt. Hamiguitan (>25%) could be due to its condition having an ultramafic soil, in which only selected plants that have high tolerance to heavy metals are able to grow so the composition of the faunal species specifically birds are also selected due to the availability of food in the area. Generally, species responds to variables correlated with gradient such as climate and factors like local climate, ecotones, competition, habitat structure, and heterogeneity play a prominent role in determining species diversity at local levels [26].

8. Heaney, L. R., E.A. Rickart, D.S. Balete, R.C.B. Uzzurum and P.C. Gonzales, 1999. Mammalian diversity on Mount Isarog, a threatened center of endemism on southern Luzon Island, Philippines. *Fieldiana: Zoology*, 95:1-62.
9. Nuñez, O.M., F.B. Ates, A.A. Alicante, M.R. Calizo-Enguito, A.G. Toledo-Bruno, Y.I. Labajo and S.M. Dejarne, 2006. Vertebrate Faunal Diversity and Relevant Interrelationships of Critical Resources in Mt. Malindang. In: *Society, Environment and Development: Mt Malindang Range. Compendium of Papers Presented in Scientific Conferences by the Biodiversity Research Programme (BRP) Researchers and Collaborators*, pp: 37-65.
10. UNESCO, 2009. Mount Apo. Retrieved from <http://whc.unesco.org/en/tentativelists/5485/>.
11. Relox, R.E., E.M. Leaño and F.A. Camino, 2011. Avifaunal assemblage in Mt. Hamiguitan, Davao Oriental, Mindanao Island, Philippines. *Journal of Environmental Science and Management*, 14(1): 1-11.
12. Peterson, A.T., T. Brooks, A. Gamauf, J.C.T. Gonzalez, N.A. Mallari, G. Dutson, S.E. Bush, D.H. Clayton and R. Fernandez, 2008. The Avifauna of Mt. Kitanglad, Bukidnon Province, Mindanao, Philippines. *Fieldiana Zoology n.s.*, 114: 1-43.
13. Alcala, A.C., E.L. Alcala, L.E. Buot, A. Diesmos, M. Dolar, E.S. Fernando, J. Gonzales and B. Tabaranza, 2006. Philippine Biodiversity: Ecological Roles, Uses, and Conservation Status. *Trans. Natl. Acad. Sci. Tech. Philippines*, 28:203-214.
14. Rasmussen, P., D.N.S. Callen, N.J. Collar, B. Demeulemeester, R.O. Hutchinson, P.G.C. Jakosalem, R.S. Kennedy, F.R. Lambert and L.M. Paguntalan, 2012. Vocal divergence and new species in the Philippine Hawk Owl *Ninox philippensis* complex. *Forktail*, 28: 1-20.
15. BirdLife International, 2008. State of the World's Birds: indicator for our changing world. BirdLife International, Cambridge, UK. ISBN 978-0-946888-63-4. Retrieved from http://www.birdlife.org/datazone/userfiles/docs/SOWB2008_en.pdf.
16. Mallari, N.A., N. Collar, D.C. Lee, P.J.K. McGowan, R. Wilkinson and S.J. Marsden, 2011. Population densities of understorey birds across a habitat gradient in Palawan, Philippines: implications for conservation. *Oryx*, 45: 234-242.
17. Mallari, N.A.D., 2009. Maximising the value of ecological and socio-economic data in support of conservation planning for key understorey bird species in Palawan, Philippines. PhD thesis, Manchester Metropolitan University, Manchester, UK.
18. Amoroso, V.B., 2006. International Long Term Ecological Research Network. In *Proceedings of the 2nd Symposium on Long-Term Ecological and Biodiversity Research in East Asia Region: 25-26 October 2006*. Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines.
19. Alcala, A. C., 2006. Status and Prospects of Long-term Research in the Philippines with an emphasis on land vertebrates and top predatory fish. *Second Symposium on Long-Term Ecological and Biodiversity Research in the East Asia Region 2006*. Central Mindanao University, Musuan, Bukidnon, Philippines.
20. [www.newsbytes.ph](http://newsbytes.ph), 2013. Smart, Sun Cellular complete network synergies in Mindanao Retrieved from <http://newsbytes.ph/2013/10/17/smart-sun-cellular-complete-network-synergies-inmindanao/>.
21. Shiu, H.J. and P.F. Lee, 2003. Seasonal Variation in Bird Species Richness along Elevational Gradients in Taiwan. *Acta Zoologica Taiwanica*, 14(1): 1 -21.
22. McCoy, E. D., 1990. The distribution of insects along elevation gradients. *Oikos*, 58: 313-322.
23. Rahbek, C., 1995. The elevational gradient of species richness: a uniform pattern?. *Ecography*, 18: 200-205.
24. Hofer, U, L.F. Bersier and D. Borcard, 1999. Spatial organization of herpetofauna on an elevational gradient. *Ecology*, 80(3): 976-988.
25. Waterhouse, F.L., M.H. Mather and D. Seip, 2002. Distribution and abundance of birds relative to elevation and biogeoclimatic zones in coastal old – growth forests in southern British Columbia. *B.C. journal of Ecosystem and Management*, 2(2): 1-13.
26. Joshi, K. K., D. Bhatt and A. Thapliyal, 2012. Avian diversity and its association with vegetation structure in different elevational zones of Nainital district (Western Himalayan) of Uttarakhand. *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 4(11): 364-376.
27. Cagod, B.M. and O.M. Nuñez, 2012. Avian species diversity in oil palm plantations of Agusan Del Sur and Compostela Valley, Philippines. *AES Bioflux*, 4(2):85-105.
28. Laurance, W.F., H.E.M. Nascimento, S.G. Laurance, A. Andrade, R.M. Ewers, K.E. Harms, R.C.C. Luizão and J.E. Ribeiro, 2007. Habitat Fragmentation, Variable Edge Effects, and the Landscape-Divergence Hypothesis. *PLoS ONE*, 2(10): e1017.
29. Amoroso, V.B. and R.A. Aspiras, 2011. Hamiguitan Range: A sanctuary for native flora. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 18: 7-15.
30. Maleri, R., S.A. Reinecke, J. Mesjasz-Przybylowicz and A.J. Reinecke, 2007. Growth and Reproduction of Earthworms in Ultramafic Soils. *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 52: 363-370.

31. Kumar, A. and S.K. Maiti, 2013. Availability of Chromium, Nickel and Other Associated Heavy Metals of Ultramafic and Serpentine Soil /Rock and in Plants. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, 3(2): 256-268.
32. Kazakou, E., P.G. Dimitrakopoulos, A.J.M. Baker, R.D. Reeves and A.Y. Troumbis, 2008. Hypotheses, mechanisms and trade-offs of tolerance and adaptation to serpentine soils: from species to ecosystem level. *Biol. Rev.*, 83: 495–508.
33. Whittaker, R.H., 1954. The ecology of serpentine soils: IV. The vegetational response to serpentine soils. *Ecology*, 35: 275–287.
34. Cousin, J.A. and R.D. Phillips, 2008. Habitat complexity explains species-specific occupancy but not species richness in a Western Australian woodland. *Australian Journal of Zoology*, 56: 95–102.
35. Klapproth, J.C. and J.E. Johnson, 2009. Understanding the Science behind Riparian Forest Buffers: Effects on Plant and Animal Communities. Virginia Cooperative Extension, pp: 420-155.
36. Mallari, N.A.D., N.J. Collar, D.C. Lee, P.J.K. McGowan, R. Wilkinson and S.J. Marsden, 2011. Population densities of understorey birds across a habitat gradient in Palawan, Philippines: implications for conservation. *Oryx*, 45(2): 234–242.
37. Paz, S.L., D. Ngoprasert, O.M. Nuñez, N.A.D. Mallari and G.A. Gale, 2013. Philippine-endemic and Mindanao-endemic Bird Communities on Caticol and Mt. Hilong-hilong, Philippines. *Asian Journal of Biodiversity*, 4(1): 135-168.
38. Ates, F.B., R.E. Relox, S.T. Bastian, E.P. Leaño, E.B. Sumile and V.B. Amoroso, 2007. Inventory and Conservation of Mammals, Birds, Reptiles and Amphibians in Mt. Hamiguitan and its Environs, Davao Oriental. Technical Report.
39. Turner, C., A. Tamblin, R. Dray, L. Maunder and P. Raines, 2003. The biodiversity of the Upper Imbang-Caliban Watershed, North Negros Forest Reserve, Negros Occidental, Philippines. Technical Publication of the Negros Rainforest Conservation Project: A Collaborative Initiative between the Negros Forests and Ecological Foundation, Inc and Coral Cay Conservation. Coral Cay Conservation Ltd., London, pp: 4-79.
40. UNESCO, 2014. Philippines Mount Hamiguitan Range Wildlife Sanctuary Becomes A Unesco World Heritage Site. Retrieved March 22, 2015 from <http://www.unesco.gov.ph/content/article/%20MOUNT%20HAMIGUITAN%20RANGE>.
41. Regalado, E., 2014. Mt. Hamiguitan nominated as World Heritage Site. <http://www.philstar.com/headlines/2014/06/18/1336020/mt.-hamiguitan-nominated-world-heritage-site>.
42. Crompton, T.R. 2001. Determination of Metals and Anions in Soils, Sediments and Sludges. CRC Press, USA, p. 241.
43. Evanko, C.R. and D.A. Dzombak, 1997. Remediation of metals-contaminated soils and groundwater. Tech. Rep. TE-97-01, Ground-Water Remediation Technologies Analysis Center (GWRTAC), Pittsburgh, Pa, USA, pp: 1-47.
44. Chibuike, G.U. and S.C. Obiora, 2014. Heavy Metal Polluted Soils: Effect on Plants and Bioremediation Methods. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2014: 1-12. Article ID 752708.
45. Villanueva, J.R. and A.B. Mohagan, 2010. Diversity and Status of Odonata across Vegetation Types in Mt. Hamiguitan Wildlife Sanctuary, Davao Oriental. *Asian Journal of Biodiversity*, 1(1): 25-35.
46. Kiikkilä, O., 2003. Heavy-metal pollution and remediation of forest soil around the Harjavalta Cu-Ni smelter, in SW Finland. *Silva Fennica*, 37(3): 399–415.
47. Paracuellos, M., 2006. How can habitat selection affect the use of a wetland complex by water birds”, *Biodiversity Conservation*, 15: 4569 – 4582.
48. Lagos, N.A., P. Paolini, E. Jaramillo, C. Lovengreen, C. Duarte and H. Contreras, 2008. Environmental processes, water quality degradation, and decline of water bird populations in the Rio cruces wetland, Chile. *Wetl.*, 28: 938 – 950.
49. Ramamurthy, V. and R. Rajakumar, 2014. A study of avifaunal diversity and Influences of water quality in the Udhayamarthandapuram bird sanctuary, Tiruvarur district, Tamil Nadu, India. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 3(1): 8851-8858.
50. Stevens, N.J. and P.M. O’Connor, 2006. Abiotic and Biotic Factors as Predictors of Species Richness on Madagascar. In Lehman SM, Fleagle JG, Eds. *Primate Biogeography*. Springer: New York, pp: 269-300.
51. Assunção-Albuquerque, M.J.T., J.R. Benayas, M.A. Rodríguez and F.S. Albuquerque, 2012. Geographic patterns of vertebrate diversity and identification of relevant areas for conservation in Europe. *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation*, 35(1): 1-11.
52. Cueto, V.R. and J.L. de Casenave, 1999. Determinants of bird species richness: role of climate and vegetation structure at a regional scale. *Journal of Biogeography*, 26: 487–492.